

UNIVERSIDAD DE INVESTIGACIÓN DE TECNOLOGÍA EXPERIMENTAL YACHAY

Escuela de Ciencias Químicas e Ingeniería

TÍTULO: Strategy for spin manipulation using cations

Trabajo de integración curricular presentado como requisito para la
obtención del título de Químico

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Urcuquí, Mayo de 2024

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Dedication

To my parents and my beloved sister.

Diana Gabriela Heredia Pardo

Acknowledgment

For my tutor Titi, who has not only been a teacher but also a cherished friend, I will forever treasure the joy and laughter we shared while working together.

Diana Gabriela Heredia Pardo

Resumen

El espín electrónico ha despertado gran interés en la comunidad científica. Una aplicación particular se encuentra en el campo de la computación cuántica, donde el espín puede utilizarse como qubit, ya que sus estados de “up” y “down” pueden traducirse en los 0 y 1 utilizados en el código binario. En este sentido, el espín electrónico sería la unidad cuántica de información más simple. Sin embargo, el principal desafío ha sido poder mantener un espín en un estado determinado o ser capaz de manipularlo de manera precisa. Por lo tanto, comprender la manipulación del espín a través de estímulos externos ha sido clave para el futuro de la computación cuántica.

El presente trabajo se centra en estudiar la interacción entre cationes y espín. Para ello, seleccionamos un modelo simple: cables moleculares, en este caso cadenas de carbono conjugadas que van desde 4 hasta 10 átomos de carbono, terminadas en hibridación sp^3/sp^2 . Estos sistemas presentan transferencia de carga bien conocida en su interior. De este modo, comparamos cables moleculares solos y en presencia de cationes. Los cationes utilizados son Litio+1 y Sodio+1, acercándose de uno a cuatro direcciones, evaluando la distribución de espín y el efecto de la presencia de cationes. En este estudio teórico, utilizamos métodos como HF, DFT y Post-HF. Un resultado interesante es la influencia del catión sobre los orbitales alfa y beta; se deforman en mayor o menor medida según la dirección de enfoque. Además de la distribución de espín, otros aspectos del cable se ven alterados, como la geometría, la distribución de electrones y, en menor medida, las longitudes de enlace.

Palabras Clave:

Cables moleculares, Cationes, Manipulación de espín, población de espín

Abstract

The electronic spin has been subject of passionate interest in the scientific community. One particular application is in the field of quantum computing, where the electronic spin can be used as qubit, given that its up and down states can be translated into 0s and 1s used in binary code. In this aspect, spin would be the simplest quantum of information. However, the main challenge has been to be able to keep a spin in a certain state, or to be capable to manipulate precisely. Therefore, understanding spin manipulation through external stimulus has been a key towards a future of quantum computing.

The present work focuses on studying the interaction between cations and spin. Then, we selected a simple model: molecular wires, i.e. conjugated carbon chains ranging from 4 to 10 carbon atoms terminated in sp^3/sp^2 hybridization. These systems present well-known charge transfer within them. Thereby, we compare bare molecular wires and in the presence of cations. The cations used are Lithium+1 and Sodium+1, approaching from one to four cations and evaluate the spin distribution and the effect of cation presence. This study is theoretical, using several levels of theory, including HF, DFT, and Post-HF. An interesting result is the influence of the cation over the alpha and beta orbitals; they are deformed to a greater or lesser extent depending on the direction of approach. In addition to spin distribution, other aspects of the wire are changed, such as geometry, electron distribution, and, to a lesser extent, bond lengths.

Keywords:

Molecular wires, Cations, Spin manipulation, spin population

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Background

1.1.1 Spintronic

Spintronics, short for spin transport electronics, is a field of electronics that focuses on the role of spin in the manipulation, transport, and control of electrons, aiming to harness the intrinsic angular momentum of electrons for developing advanced electronic devices and technologies[3, 4]. With the development of this field the flux of electrons can be described by the charge and the spin orientation, the preferred spin orientation is called spin polarization.

Some applications of spintronics are in ferromagnetic and antiferromagnetic materials that the spin orientation allows to their magnetic properties. The magnetic random access memory devices uses the mechanism spin-transfer torque that involves the transfer of spin angular momentum between electrons in a magnetic layer and a neighboring layer[5]. Topological insulators uses the quantum spin Hall effect where electron spins are locked to their momentum, providing a platform for creating dissipationless edge states[6]. These surface states can potentially be used to create robust qubits, the basic units of quantum information.

With the use of the spin in electronics devices, some potential advantages in term of speed, efficiency and functionality begin to emerge. The use of spin provides quantum properties to devices, such as: quantum entanglement which can be harnessed for instantaneous transfer of quantum information. In the context of spintronics, entanglement between electrons can contribute to efficient transmission of quantum information and the creation of collective quantum states[7]. Spin interference can be used to control the propagation of spins through different paths in spintronic devices. This can lead to the creation of devices with novel functionalities, such as spin interferometers, allowing quantum spin manipulation. Long-range spin coherence is essential for the creation of quantum spin qubits and coherent transmission of quantum information over considerable distances[8].

1.1.2 Quantum Theory and Spin

With the develop of the quantum theory phenomenons coming from matter and energy at the smallest scales start to have a explanation. Introducing probabilistic concepts and the quantization of phenomenons; quantum theory is able to explain key aspect such as wave-particle duality, superposition of particles, uncertainty principle, quantum entanglement, quantum tunneling, spin, among others. The most famous quantum equation is the Schrödinger equation presented by him in 1926 in his work “Quantization as an Eigenvalue Problem”[9]; and describes the evolution of a quantum system through the time. This equation is a eigenvalue problem which looks for solutions such that when the Hamiltonian operator be apply over wave function ψ the result must be a number (that say eigenvalue E) multiplying by the same wave function, mathematically expressed by $\hat{H}\psi = E\psi$, where \hat{H} is the Hamiltonian operator, which represent the total energy of the system, ψ is the wave function, which describes the quantum state of a system and E is the energy related to the quantum system described by ψ .

The Schrödinger equation, in its general form, is derived for an uncharged and non-relativistic particle. A way to study one of the spin interactions, is through the an additional term known as Spin-Orbit coupling (SOC). SOC was proposed by George E. Uhlenbeck and Samuel A. Goudsmit in 1925[10]. They introduced the concept of intrinsic angular momentum associated with the electron, now known as “spin.” This intrinsic angular momentum, when combined with the electron’s orbital angular momentum, contributes to the total angular momentum of the electron in an atom.

Figure 1.1: SOC representation in an one-electron atom. The blue arrows depict the orbital \mathbf{L} and spin \mathbf{S} angular momenta which therefore play the role of j_1 and j_2 in the coupled representation.

SOC is a relativistic interaction that arises from the interplay between a particle's intrinsic spin and its movement within a potential field. In the realm of chemistry, a prominent example involves the interaction of an electron's spin with the electromagnetic field it experiences as it orbits the positively charged nucleus. This interaction influences atomic energy levels, leading to a phenomenon known as fine structure in atomic spectra. Fine structure manifests as a splitting of spectral lines, akin to a Zeeman effect caused by the apparent magnetic field from the electron's viewpoint and its own magnetic moment.

Thus, its proposed a special Hamiltonian which uses a particular division of energy to highlight the SOC operator. This equation can be applied to a charged particle in an electromagnetic field, and is expressed as:

$$\hat{H}\Psi = \left[\frac{\hat{p}^2}{2m} + V(\mathbf{r}) + \hat{V}_{SO}(\mathbf{r}) \right] \Psi = E\Psi \quad (1.1)$$

Where:

- \hat{H} is the Hamiltonian operator
- ψ is the system wave function.
- \hat{p} is the lineal momentum operator
- m is the particle mass
- $V(r)$ is the potential that depends on the position
- $\hat{V}_{SO}(r)$ is the SOC operator

The specific form of SOC term depends on the particle type and the context of the target problem. In the case of particles with $\pm 1/2$ spin, like the electron, the SOC term can be expressed as:

$$\hat{V}_{SO}(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{\hbar}{4m^2c^2} \frac{1}{r} \frac{dV(\mathbf{r})}{dr} \hat{\mathbf{L}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{S}} \quad (1.2)$$

Where:

- \hbar is the Planck constant.
- c is the light speed
- r is the distance from center of the field
- \hat{L} is the orbital angular moment operator
- \hat{S} is the spin operator

Another proposal to incorporate the SOC term is through relativistic extensions, like the Dirac equation. It takes account the relativistic effects thus provides a more accuracy description of the behavior of subatomic particles[11]. The solution of this equation gives four components of the wave function (includes the anti-particles), which implicates the spin existence.

$$(i\gamma^\mu \partial_\mu - mc)\psi = 0 \quad (1.3)$$

Where:

- ψ represents the wave function of the particle
- i is the imaginary unit
- γ^μ are the gamma matrices
- ∂_μ is the partial derivative with respect to the spacetime coordinate
- m is the rest mass of the particle
- c is the speed of light in vacuum

Paul Dirac in 1928 proposed the Gamma matrices to represent the Dirac equation in a compact and relativistically covariant manner. These matrices describes the effect of a spinor (a special type of mathematical object that describes the spin of a particle) under a rotation or Lorentz transformation, these matrices are used. There are four gamma matrices:

$$\gamma^0 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad \gamma^1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \gamma^2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & -i \\ 0 & 0 & i & 0 \\ 0 & i & 0 & 0 \\ -i & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \gamma^3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Gamma matrices have important properties, such as:

- They are unitary matrices, meaning that they preserve the inner product of a vector space.
- They are Hermitian, meaning that they are equal to their adjoints.
- They achieve the Clifford algebra.
- They satisfy the anticommutation relation, which states that the product of any two gamma matrices is equal to the negative of the product of the same two matrices in the opposite order.

There is a fifth matrix called γ^5 , which is defined as the product of the all gamma matrices:

$$\gamma^5 = i\gamma^0\gamma^1\gamma^2\gamma^3 \quad (1.4)$$

This matrix is used to distinguish between particles and antiparticles in a theory known as chiral symmetry. It also plays an important role in the study of quantum anomalies.

1.1.3 Spin description

The discovery of electron spin was a result of the Stern–Gerlach experiment, which demonstrated that electrons possess an intrinsic angular momentum with two possible orientations in a magnetic field, later identified as spin up and down[12]. The spin is not related to physical rotation but behaves as if the particle is spinning on its axis. However, it's important to note that the concept of “spin” in the context of quantum mechanics is a purely mathematical description and should not be interpreted as a classical spinning motion, spin exist as a manifestation of quantum nature of electron. The spin can be measure in other elementary particles, such as quarks, leptons, protons, and neutrons. The particles which has only two possibility of spin (up or down) are classified like Fermions. These two states are what allow them to interact with the magnetic field. Some key aspect related to the spin are following:

- **Quantization:** Spin is quantized, meaning it can only take on discrete values. For elementary particles, the spin can be expressed in units of $\hbar/2$, where \hbar is the reduced Planck constant.
- **Intrinsic Property:** Spin is considered an intrinsic property of particles, meaning it is a fundamental characteristic that cannot be explained in terms of more basic properties. It is not associated with any measurable spatial dimension.
- **Spin States:** Particles with half-integer spin, such as electrons ($S = 1/2$), are fermions and obey Fermi-Dirac statistics. Particles with integer spin, like photons ($S = 1$), are bosons and obey Bose-Einstein statistics.
- **Pauli Exclusion Principle:** The Pauli Exclusion Principle states that no two fermions can occupy the same quantum state simultaneously. Electron spin is a fundamental factor in enforcing this principle, as two electrons in the same orbital must have different spin states.

The mathematics representation of spin is made by Pauli matrices[13]. There are three Pauli matrices, commonly denoted as σ_x , σ_y , and σ_z , and they are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_x &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \\ \sigma_y &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{pmatrix} \\ \sigma_z &= \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}\end{aligned}\tag{1.5}$$

These matrices has important features as: hermitian which means that they are equal to their conjugate transpose, unitary, meaning the product of the matrix and its conjugate transpose is the identity matrix. These matrices satisfy certain Clifford algebra relations, which are important in the mathematical description of spin. Finally, Pauli matrices are involved in the Pauli equation, which describes the behavior of fermions in the presence of

an external magnetic fields.

The Pauli equation is a relativistic quantum mechanical equation. It is an extension of the Schrödinger equation and incorporates relativistic effects, specifically the spin of particles, hence it provides a more accurate description than the non-relativistic Schrödinger equation when the speeds of the particles approach a significant fraction of the speed of light or when the external fields are strong[14]. The Pauli equation is as follows:

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial t} = \left[\frac{1}{2m} (\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot (\mathbf{p} - q\mathbf{A}))^2 + q\phi + V(\mathbf{r}) \right] \Psi \quad (1.6)$$

Here, the terms represent the following:

- $\hbar \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial t}$: The time-dependent part of the wavefunction
- $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$: The vector of Pauli matrices, representing the spin operators
- \mathbf{p} : The momentum operator
- q : The charge of the particle
- \mathbf{A} : The vector potential of the external magnetic field
- ϕ : The scalar potential of the external electric field
- $V(r)$: The external potential

1.1.4 Quantum Information and Spin States

Quantum theory is the foundation of quantum computing, a field that explores the use of quantum states (qubits) to perform information processing tasks with potentially superior efficiency compared to classical computers for certain problems. Spin states, particularly those associated with electron spin, are essential for implementing qubits in various quantum technologies.

The use of spin allows superior velocity in transmitting information, thanks to the superposition and entanglement properties. In the case of classical bits, information transmission relies on electrical signals, where the presence or absence of an electric charge represents binary states (0 or 1)[15]. Qubits based on spin, can exist in superpositions of states, enabling the representation of both 0 and 1 simultaneously. Additionally, the entanglement allows the instantaneous correlation of states between entangled qubits, providing a means of communication that doesn't rely on traditional electrical signals. Furthermore, the size of an electron is immensely small, which allows much more information to be stored in the same volume. These unique characteristics of spin-based qubits hold promise for the development of faster and more efficient quantum communication systems compared to classical information transmission methods.

The spin as qubits can be manipulated through quantum gates to perform operations such as spin flips, superposition, and entanglement creation, enabling the implementation of quantum algorithms[16]. The last, is used for quantum communication protocols like quantum key distribution. Here, changes in spin states can be detected, ensuring the security of the transmitted quantum information. Another example is the spin-photon entanglement that can be utilized for long-distance quantum communication[17]. Changes in spin states can be correlated with changes in photon polarization, providing a means of information transfer. Additionally, the spin as qubit can also be implemented quantum dot-based quantum computing architectures. Quantum dots are semiconductor-based artificial materials that can trap and confine electrons. First, qubits are initialized by preparing electron spins in a defined state within the quantum dots. Then, quantum gates and operations are applied to manipulate the spin states. Thereby, the final state, representing the quantum information, can be read out by measuring the spin state of the electrons[18].

1.1.5 Cations and spin

Cations, with their positive charge, can influence electrons. As spin is an intrinsic property of electrons, it can also be affected by the presence of cations. The impact on electrons depends on the intensity of the positive charge and the proximity of the cation. An illustrative example is the influence on SOC. SOC is a subtle interaction between the spin of an electron and its motion around the atomic nucleus. The perturbation caused by a positive charge alters the motion of electrons, resulting in changes to their spin properties. The cations also be used to doping materials to control of spin states. Here, cations can act as charge carriers and modify the electronic structure of the material. Therefore, may influence the spin states of electrons and contribute to the creation of spin-polarized currents. Previous studied results in materials that incorporate cations as spin-active centers[19], where the magnetic behavior is strongly influenced by the presence and arrangement of these cations. This can lead to materials with tunable magnetic and spin properties. Thereby, the introduction of cations in a material may be tailored to achieve desired spin properties and functionalities.

1.1.6 Theoretical developments and computational modeling

In a material, electronic properties are studied using different approaches depending on the objective of the study. Starting with the fastest methods: molecular dynamics. This method allows the study of dynamic behavior and interactions of atoms and molecules over time. It provides insights into the motion, conformational changes, and thermodynamic properties of a system at the molecular level[20].

Monte Carlo simulation is stochastic (probabilistic) computational method that provide statistical sampling of possible configurations of a system. The system's energy is typically described by an energy function or potential energy surface, which includes terms for bonding, non-bonded interactions, and other relevant contributions. Monte Carlo simulations involve making random configurational changes to the system, such as changes in

atomic positions or molecular conformations. These changes are proposed based on probability distributions, allowing exploration of various configurations. However, the speed of calculations in this method is due to the approximations made, resulting in significant limitations when studying finer properties, such those related with electrons.

Models that solve the Schrödinger equations are developed to study electron properties in-depth. For example, ab-initio DFT is a model that does not depend on experimentally adjusted parameters but instead deals with electron density to perform accurate calculations. Examples of software that work with DFT in materials are Quantum ESPRESSO and VASP. For molecular DFT calculations, software like Orca and Gaussian are employed. Another method is post-Hartree Fock; this approach calculates the electronic properties of a selected set of electrons with the highest accuracy by considering all possible two-electron interactions in the active space. Software that work with are: Molcas, Gamess, NWChem, MOLPRO, and so on.

1.2 Problem statement

How is the information stored? How can we store music, photos, or movies (memories) in a multidimensional space to access their information whenever we want and make it perceptible to the senses? In the language of informatics, any information can be translated into 0s and 1s (binary code) and then stored in the “cloud”, which is a set of memories mainly made of magnets that physically contain its 0s and 1s. But again the 0 and 1 are complex (abstract) concepts that are not physically present. Then a bigger question emerges: how we can get a 0 or 1 to store our favorite song? Classically, information is typically stored and processed using electronic circuits, such as transistors. These circuits manipulate electrical voltages to represent binary states. The presence or absence of electrical charge corresponds to the binary values 0 and 1. Thus, the data transmission involves the manipulation of electrical signals to convey information between different components, such as the CPU, memory, and input/output devices.

Another strategy is materialize these 0s and 1s by a phenomenon even more interesting, the spin. By convention, spin-up is considered 0, and spin-down is considered 1. Despite the fact that the matter of an atom is considered around 99.9% void, a minuscule part of this matter is composed of electrons, which, advantageously have spin as a natural characteristic, like many other subatomic particles. But why are the spins of electrons so special? Fermionic particles have spin $\pm 1/2$, precisely two options (0 and 1). This spin state is not fixed, and we can externally manipulate it. The mechanism to transition between up and down states has become an exciting field of research. Motivated by recent developments in this project, we are investigating strategies for spin manipulation using cations.

1.3 Objectives

1.3.1 General Objective

Understand the influence of cations on the spin state in molecular systems, through theoretical calculations, to design strategies for spin manipulation possibly applicable in spintronic devices.

1.3.2 Specific Objectives

- Decipher molecular wires properties and their change with length
- Evaluate the effect of a cation on the spin distribution
- Understand if the length has an effect on the changes observed
- Compare the changes produced by two cations with different ionic potentials: Li^+ and Na^+
- Evaluate the effect of the numbers and position of cations present
- Decide from all the results which cation and position affect more the spin distribution and, from it, propose a strategy for molecular electronic design

Chapter 2

Theoretical Framework

2.1 Molecular wires

Wire is a elongated material that typically connect two parts of a device, enabling communication through various signals. The type of information that a wire can manipulate depends on its nature. While charge is the most common, a sufficiently sensitive wire can also react to mechanical pressure.

Wires can be crafted from diverse materials and in different manners to suit various purposes. For the scope of this work, we focus on the characteristics of molecular wire types. In contrast to conventional wires, molecular wires exhibit a molecular delicacy, making macroscopic manipulation impossible. These wires are assembled at the molecular level, with molecules connecting one by one, and in extreme cases, atom by atom[21]. Some examples of molecular wires are polyenes[22], carbon nanotubes[23], linear polymers[24], among others.

Figure 2.1: Examples of molecular wires

Molecular electronics is a field of research that seeks to create molecules with functionalities similar to known electronic components, such as diodes and transistors. These molecular wires are proposed to be used in molecular electronic devices, potentially replacing the metal and silicon-based wires found in conventional semiconductor devices[25].

Richard Feynman exposed the relevance of extremely small devices like wires in the computational world[26]. In his age, one computer occupied a whole room but now with the miniaturization of devices we can carry a computer in our backpack. Then, as the world notice the importance of manipulate small electronics for technological advances a variety of devices began to emerge. These devices integrates the molecular wires to applications such as: miniaturization of electronic devices[27], conductance and charge transport[28], single-molecule arrays[29], sensor technology[30], energy storage and conversion[31], quantum computing[32], etc.

Much of the current research on molecular wires primarily emphasizes charge transportation, often overlooking the significant aspect of spin. Then, they study the flow of electrons, which facilitates the transport of charge through a wire. So, it is essential to note that electrons, in addition to carrying charge, possess another critical property: the spin. As previously mentioned, spin can exist in one of two states: up or down. Exploiting the distinct spin states of electrons opens a new pathway for representing the binary code (1 and 0) essential for computation.

Thanks to the small size of molecular wires, quantum effects play a relevant role. For example the quantum tunneling, which is the phenomenon where electrons can pass through energy barriers. In molecular wires, the ability to facilitate quantum tunneling can impact electron transport across the wire[33]. Other example is the quantum interference effects, that can lead to unique conductivity patterns in molecular wires, and they are influenced by the specific arrangement of atoms and electronic states within the wire[34]. Also, quantum coherent electron transport allows for efficient and long-range energy transfer, contributing to the overall conductivity and functionality of molecular wires[35].

The use of a molecule as a molecular wire offers some features that are desirable, for example a intrinsic conductivity; a highly conductive facilitates the efficient transport of electrons, which is essential for electronic devices. The electrical conductivity can be studied with the energy band structure, which tell us the allowed energy levels, then quantify their electrical conductivity and the electronic transport properties. Also, a small HOMO-LUMO gap is generally associated with better electrical conductivity. This gap is the energy difference between the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO).

2.1.1 Charge transport mechanism in molecular wires

The type of charge transport mechanism is crucial to evaluate the efficiency in conducting charge. The two mechanisms in molecular wires are hopping and coherent tunneling[36].

Hopping transport, also known as charge hopping, involves the sequential transfer of charge carriers (typically electrons) between localized states within a molecular system. Here, electrons move as jumping between adjacent molecular orbitals or sites, it is mathematically represented as the hopping integral. The charge carrier is localized on one site, and due to thermal fluctuations or other factors, it can hop to an adjacent site. This process

repeats as electrons move through the material. The rate of hopping is often temperature-dependent. At higher temperatures, thermal energy facilitates the movement of charge carriers, increasing the hopping rate. Hopping transport is associated with localized electron states. The charge carriers spend most of their time localized on specific molecular sites before hopping to nearby sites. Hopping transport is common in disordered or amorphous molecular systems, where a regular, extended molecular structure may be absent[37].

Coherent Tunneling is a quantum mechanical process in which charge carriers tunnel through a barrier without losing phase coherence. As the electrons exhibit wave-like behavior, they can penetrate energy barriers as if they were waves passing through a classically forbidden region. The tunneling process maintains the phase relationship between the initial and final states, also coherent tunneling is highly dependent on the overlap of the wavefunctions of the initial and final states. Then, when there is a significant overlap, the tunneling probability is higher. Coherent tunneling becomes more prominent when the barriers are thin, and the energy levels of the initial and final states are well-matched. It is often observed in well-defined, ordered molecular systems with relatively low disorder. Coherent tunneling can exhibit quantum interference effects, where multiple pathways contribute to the overall tunneling probability. This interference can lead to enhanced or suppressed tunneling rates[38].

The dominance of either hopping or coherent tunneling charge transport mechanisms in materials depends on various factors such as the material's properties, structure, and environmental conditions. Both mechanisms can contribute to charge transport in different scenarios. But in general materials with disorder and weak electronic coupling often exhibit hopping transport, while well-ordered and strongly coupled materials may demonstrate coherent tunneling. The preference of one mechanism over the other is made by the application, for example in semiconductor devices, coherent tunneling is often desirable for achieving high electron mobility and efficient charge transfer[39]. In molecular electronics may benefit from both mechanisms, depending on the nature of the molecular wire and its integration into devices.

2.1.2 Polyenes

Polyenes are a class of organic compounds (hydrocarbons) characterized by a chain of alternating single and multiple (double or triple) bonds. The conjugated system allows delocalization of π -electrons along the entire chain, thus give rise to distinctive electronic and optical properties; making them interesting for various applications. Polyenes can be classified based on the number of double bonds they contain. Conjugated dienes have two double bonds, while conjugated trienes have three and so on.

Thanks their conjugated structure, polyenes often exhibit color. As an example, polyenes are often found in natural chromophores, molecules responsible for the coloration of various biological compounds. One of them are the carotenoids, which contribute to the color of many fruits and vegetables. The absorption of light corresponds to the π -electron transitions. The longer the conjugated chain, the more extended the absorption into the visible spectrum, resulting in a deeper color[40]. The conjugated double bonds in polyenes can

undergo isomerization and photoisomerization reactions, which are relevant in biological processes and molecular switches.

The length of the polyenes are very important, because, a long chain means a large π conjugated system, and as the conjugation increases the HOMO-LUMO gap is reduced (see fig. 2.2), therefore, the conductivity is facilitated.

Figure 2.2: HOMO-LUMO gap reduction in function of the chain length. The corresponding energy and wave length is also show. Adapted from “L’Effet d’interfaces electrodes couche active sur les performances de la cellule solaire organique à base de P3HT : PCBM” [1]

2.2 Close and open shell molecules

- Close shell molecules (CSM): molecules which each molecular orbital is doubly occupied.
- Open shell molecules (OSM): molecules which has at least one singly occupied molecular orbital.

The core of chemistry lies in the electrons and their positions in orbitals, directing reactivity and other interactions. For CSM, only the Pauli exclusion principle and the Slater determinant must be satisfied. In CSM, if two electrons are exchanged, such a function remains unchanged by any unitary transformation of the doubly occupied orbitals. In the case of OSM, as the orbital is singly occupied, its electron can adopt either an up or down spin state. Therefore, it becomes important to discriminate between alpha and beta spin states.

2.3 Alpha and Beta orbitals

Follow the molecular orbital theory, the terms alpha and beta are used to distinguish between the spin state of two electrons belonging the same orbital. The exclusion principle Pauli's statement that two electrons in the same orbital (also in ground state) must have opposite spin directions, then, alpha term is used to spin up ($m_s = +1/2$) and beta term for spin down ($m_s = -1/2$). This also ensures that there are no two electrons with the same four quantum numbers.

In OSM, unpaired electrons can freely assume either the alpha or beta state, as their energies remain equal unless influenced by an external field. Electron spin can interact with a magnetic field, aligning with it in the case of OSM, they said to be paramagnetic systems. This alignment is favored because when the electron spin is parallel to the magnetic field, the energy is reduced, resulting in greater stability compared to the scenario where the electron spin is opposite to the external field. In CSM, electrons within doubly occupied orbitals exist in both the alpha and beta states, effectively canceling out their interaction with the external magnetic field, and said to be diamagnetic systems.

The total number of alpha and beta electrons in a molecule are employed to calculate the multiplicity through the total spin.

$$S = (\# \text{ of alpha electrons})(+1/2) + (\# \text{ of beta electrons})(-1/2) \quad (2.1)$$

$$\text{Multiplicity} = |2S| + 1 \quad (2.2)$$

2.4 Spin state of molecules

Spin state or multiplicity of spin appear to distinguish between the different spin configurations. Depending of their alpha or beta dispositions and the energy level; the molecules can be classified in singlet (multiplicity of 1), doublet (multiplicity of 2), triplet (multiplicity of 3) and so on.

Figure 2.3: Graphical representation of spin multiplicity. The triplet two electron unpaired is the $m_s = +1$ component

2.5 Spin-spin interactions

The spin-spin interactions are a phenomenon that involves the mutual influence of the spins of quantum particles, such as electrons, protons, and other Fermionic particles. The most fundamental spin-spin interaction is known as electronic exchange. This interaction describes how the total wave function of an electron system changes when the positions of two electrons are exchanged, taking into account their spins[41, 42]. Additionally there are a energy associated of this phenomenon called exchange energy and that causes electronic structures of greater multiplicity to have lower energy (Hund's first rule). The term "exchange" comes from this swapping of positions.

Another spin-spin interaction is the Heisenberg exchange interaction. It is a generalization of exchange interaction, and it is commonly used in the Heisenberg model to describe magnetic interactions in materials. This interaction arises from the mutual coupling of magnetic moments associated with the intrinsic spins of electrons in a material[43]. Here the electron spin is influenced by the neighboring particles, resulting in magnetic moments align either in parallel (ferromagnetic interaction) or in anti-parallel (antiferromagnetic interaction). The Heisenberg Exchange interaction gives rise to excitations known as spin waves or magnons. Spin waves represent collective oscillations of spins in a magnetic material and are crucial for understanding magnetic dynamics.

Quantum entanglement arises from the spin-spin interactions, here, the states of two or more particles become correlated, even when separated by large distances. The entanglement is harnessed in quantum information processing and quantum communication.

A high amount of spin-spin interactions can result in collective quantum effects, where the quantum states and behaviors of individual particles become entangled or correlated. The spin liquids is a result of collective quantum effects, in this liquids there are a conflicting interactions that prevent the material from settling into a well-defined magnetic order[44].

2.6 Spin-charge conversion

It is phenomena where the manipulation of electron spin is coupled to the generation or detection of an electrical charge current, or vice versa. Spin-charge conversion often involves SOC. In materials with strong SOC, the electron's spin becomes entangled with its orbital motion, providing a means for converting between spin and charge[45].

The direct Edelstein effect is a manifestation of spin-charge conversion. In this effect, an applied electric field induces a spin polarization perpendicular to both the electric field and the electron's motion. This spin polarization results in a charge current that flows perpendicular to both the electric field and the spin polarization. Also exist the inverse Edelstein effect, which involves the conversion of a spin current into a charge current[46]. When a spin-polarized current is injected into a material with strong SOC, it can generate

a charge current perpendicular to the spin polarization.

The Rashba-Bychkov effect is another mechanism for spin-charge conversion. It occurs at the interface of materials with structural asymmetry, leading to a spin splitting of electronic bands. An applied electric field then induces a spin-polarized charge current[47].

2.7 Spin manipulation techniques

Spin manipulation techniques refer to methods and strategies employed to control the orientation and dynamics of electron spins in various physical systems. These techniques are crucial for the field of spintronics, where the manipulation of electron spin is utilized for information processing and storage. Below are some spin manipulation techniques:

- **Electrical Spin Manipulation:** Uses the electric fields to control the orientation and dynamics of electron spins in semiconductors. One key mechanism is spin-orbit coupling, where the intrinsic interaction between the electron's spin and its motion in the presence of electric fields leads to effective magnetic fields affecting the spins. The electric field effect, where an applied voltage alters the electron's energy levels[48].
- **Optical Spin Manipulation:** Uses light and optical techniques to control electron spins. This field explores phenomena such as optical pumping and coherent control, where interactions with photons influence and manipulate the spins of electrons. Optical methods provide a non-contact and precise means of spin manipulation, with potential applications in quantum information processing and spin-based devices[49].
- **Spin-Transfer Torque:** Is a spintronic phenomenon that involves the transfer of spin angular momentum between a spin-polarized current and a magnetic layer. When a spin-polarized current is injected into a magnetic layer, it can exert a torque on the magnetization, leading to changes in the orientation of the magnetic moments. This effect is harnessed for manipulating the magnetization direction in magnetic devices[50].
- **Spin Hall Effect:** Is a phenomenon where an electric current flowing through a material leads to the generation of a transverse spin current. This effect arises due to spin-orbit coupling in materials. Here, spins are deflected perpendicular to the charge flow, creating a spin current without net charge flow[51].
- **Magnetic resonance techniques:** Such as Nuclear Magnetic Resonance and Electron Spin Resonance, are powerful tools for spin manipulation. These methods utilize the interaction between spins and external magnetic fields to probe and manipulate the spin states of nuclei or electrons in a sample[52].

2.8 Molecular orbital theory applied to molecular wires

Molecular Orbital (MO) theory is a model that describes how atomic orbitals combine to form molecular orbitals when atoms bond together to create molecule. Its model of bonds

defined that the electrons are not confined to bonds between two atoms. Instead, they occupy orbitals that are spread out over the entire molecule. These molecular orbitals are mathematically formed by adding and subtracting the wave functions of the atomic orbitals involved in the bond. The different types of orbitals created are: bond orbitals, anti-bonding orbitals and non bonding orbitals. Here the molecular orbitals have unique energy levels and the electrons fill these orbitals according to the same principles as atomic orbitals. The main contribution to MO theory was made by Friedrich Hund, Edward Lenard-Jones, Robert Mulliken and Erich Hückel.

In molecular wires, the atomic orbitals of the constituent atoms combine to create a series of molecular orbitals that span the length of the wire. The conductive properties of molecular wires are strongly influenced by the arrangement of molecular orbitals. In a conjugated system, where alternating single and double bonds create a delocalized π -system, molecular orbitals can extend over the entire wire, facilitating electron delocalization and enhancing conductivity.

To build molecular orbital diagram for poly-atomic molecules is necessary to do it by “fragments”[53, 54]. Initially, these fragments are usually made by two or three atoms, that later are joined with other “fragments” until get the desired molecule. The trans-1,3-butadiene belong to the C_{2h} symmetry point group, we made 3 fragments:

Figure 2.4: Molecular orbital diagram for CH fragment

Figure 2.5: Molecular orbital diagram for CH_2 fragment

Figure 2.6: Molecular orbital diagram for CH_2CH fragment

Figure 2.7: Molecular orbital diagram for trans-1,3-butadiene

Chapter 3

Methodology

3.1 Density Functional Theory (DFT)

DFT is a computational quantum mechanical modeling method used to study the electronic structure of atoms, molecules, and solids. This method deals with the electron density instead of solving the many-body Schrödinger equation directly. The basis for DFT calculations involves a functional and a basis set. The Exchange-correlation functional approximates the effects of electron-electron interactions, while the basis set expands the electronic wavefunction as a linear combination of these basis functions, which serve as the foundation for constructing approximate solutions to the Schrödinger equation. We can choose from a wide range of functionals, each with its own approximations and considerations. To achieve the objective of this study, the highest precision level is necessary, considering the computational cost.

3.1.1 Input parameters and software

- Functional: B3LYP; is a hybrid density functional that are composed of several components. Exchange Functional (B), developed by Perdew and Wang based on Becke's three-parameter exchange functional. This component includes a combination of local (LDA) and non-local (GGA) exchange terms. Correlation Functional (LYP), developed by Lee, Yang, and Parr. This component includes a mixture of local and non-local correlation terms. Hybrid Mixing Parameter (3): determines the proportion of Hartree-Fock exchange in the exchange-correlation functional. In the case of B3LYP, is set to 0.2, indicating a 20% contribution from Hartree-Fock exchange[55].
- Basis set: def2-TZVPP. The prefix Def2 indicated that this set is part of the "def2" series[56]. The T Stands for Triple-zeta (three sets of atomic orbitals for each type of orbital: s, p, and d). Z represents polarization functions that account for electron correlation effects. V denotes diffuse functions, which are added to capture the electron density in the outer regions of the atomic or molecular orbitals. PP indicates the use of a set of diffuse and polarization functions on heavy atoms (atoms beyond hydrogen and helium).

- Auxiliary basis set: def2-TZVPP/C. Includes the correlation-consistent functions[57].
- Dispersion correction: D4. Is part of the Grimme-D series developed by Stefan Grimme. D4 employs empirical parameters that allow for a more accurate representation of dispersion interactions[58].

To perform these calculus Orca software [59] was used. Orca, created by Frank Neese, is a free ab initio, DFT and semiempirical SCF-MO package, which counts with a great variety of functionals and basis sets.

3.2 Post Hartree-Fock (post-HF) methods

As the spin is strongly bound to the electron, the post-HF methods appear as a more suitable option because the electron-electron interactions (electronic correlation) are well-described with this approach. The post-HF solves the Schrödinger equation electron by electron (inside of the CAS) beyond the mean-field approximation, providing a more accurate description of the electronic structure. The greatest advantage of this method is its superior ability to determine the electronic properties of a specific set of electrons (active space); however, it has a high computational cost, which is considered a disadvantage, especially for large systems. Within the post-HF method, there are several approaches with their respective considerations. The two main category are Multiconfigurational SCF with programs such as CASSCF, RASSCF, GASSCF, and DMRG. Multiconfigurational perturbation theory: CASPT2, RASPT2, and GASPT2.

3.2.1 Complete Active Space Second Order Perturbation Theory (CASPT2)

CASPT2 is a extension to Complete Active Space theory (CAS) which allows for the simultaneous treatment of multiple electron correlation effects, optimum for open-shell systems or with strongly correlated electrons. The PT2 is a means second order Many-Body Perturbation Theory, which includes correlation effects as perturbative corrections to the HF wave-function.

The CAS refers to a collection of orbitals and electrons within a molecule that are anticipated to be more active in reality, playing a crucial role in determining the electronic properties of the entire molecule. The careful selection of the CAS is essential because all configuration iterations within it are calculated, and to obtain the closest representation of the real function, significant consideration must be given to the heaviest configuration iterations. Both dynamic and static correlation are taken into account within the CAS. The CAS can be subdivided into three subsets: RAS1, RAS2, and RAS3. RAS1 specifies the maximum number of holes allowed in that subset of orbitals or the maximum number of electrons that can transition to RAS2 or RAS3. RAS2 forms the core of the active space, defines the number of active orbitals, which have their own electrons and those that may come from RAS1. RAS3 specifies the maximum number of particles that can be in that subset of orbitals, and these electrons can come from either RAS1 or RAS2. The fig.3.1 is

a representations of CAS.

Figure 3.1: Representation of RAS spaces inside the CAS.

CASPT2 method needs a starting or reference (H_0) function, and the results will be dependent of that. For all calculations our reference is a HF function, which the orbitals orders was slightly altered to obtain the correct orbitals to the conjugated system. The selection of the CAS was made according to the MO's and symmetries obtained in the DFT calculation.

3.2.2 Molecular orbital theory (MOT) to construct the Active space

The basis of MOT to construct the molecular orbitals is doing a linear combination of the atomic orbitals. Constructing molecular orbitals (MOs) is relatively straightforward for diatomic molecules. However, the complexity of MOs increases with the number of atoms in a molecule. Therefore, for polyatomic molecules, MOT proposes constructing MOs from “fragments”, which are sections of the larger molecule.

The following table summarizes the symmetries of the MO's of trans-1,3-butadiene and shows the corresponding type of bond.

irrep	a_g	b_u	b_g	a_u
$(1s)_C$	2	2	0	0
$(\sigma)_{CC}$	2	1	0	0
$(\sigma)_{CH}$	3	3	0	0
$(\pi)_{CC}$	0	0	1	1
$(\pi^*)_{CC}$	0	0	1	1
$(\sigma^*)_{CC}$	2	1	0	0
$(\sigma^*)_{CH}$	3	3	0	0

Table 3.1: Orbitals of trans-1,3- butadiene separated by irrep of C_{2h} point group.

The trans-1,3- butadiene has two double bonds which are delocalized around the chain. This double bonds mainly comes from p atomic orbitals. The remaining chains have a similar system, in which one p atomic orbital from each carbon atom linearly combines with another p atomic orbital to form a π molecular orbital. The fig. 3.2 shows a graphical representation of the conjugated π system as the number of p atomic orbital increases.

Figure 3.2: π molecular orbitals of polyenes[2]

In polyenes, the HOMO and LUMO orbitals corresponds two of the π molecular orbitals, therefore, always need to be included in the CAS. This HOMO-LUMO gap can be influenced by the number of carbon atoms. For polyenes with an even number of carbons, the molecular orbitals align more symmetrically, leading to a smaller HOMO-LUMO gap. This is because the even-numbered polyenes have a central carbon-carbon double bond, and the electron distribution is spread more evenly across the molecule. On the other hand, polyenes with an odd number of carbons lack a central double bond, resulting in a larger HOMO-LUMO gap. The absence of a central double bond leads to asymmetric electron distribution, and the energy separation between the HOMO and LUMO is greater[60]. This trend in the HOMO-LUMO gap can have implications for the electronic and optical properties of polyenes, including their conductive and absorptive characteristics.

3.3 Hückel Molecular Orbital (HMO) model

Proposed by Erich Hückel in 1931[61], this method is a simplification of quantum methods used to predict the π -electron stability of conjugated systems, as well as the number of energy levels and their distribution (degeneracy). The HMO theory applies specifically to planar or nearly planar molecules, where the σ and π orbitals are orthogonal. The HMO model focuses on the delocalized π -electrons, which move over the π molecular orbitals.

To do a HMO calculation, first we need to write the π -molecular orbital Ψ (delocalized over n atoms) as a linear combination of n atomic orbitals (LCAO) ϕ_i .

$$\Psi = \sum_i c_i \phi_i \quad (3.1)$$

Where the ϕ_i 's are the atomic p_z orbitals on the atoms i .

Then, the energy E and the coefficients c_i for the ground state can be determined thanks to the variation principle, which says that E should be approximated to the lowest-energy state which is as close as possible to the true energy.

$$E = \frac{\int \Psi H \Psi d\tau}{\int \Psi^2 d\tau} = \text{minimum} \quad (3.2)$$

The coefficients c_i are obtained from the minimization relations:

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial c_i} = 0; \quad i = 1 \dots n \quad (3.3)$$

With this we set the secular equations:

$$\begin{aligned} c_1 (H_{11} - S_{11}E) + c_2 (H_{12} - S_{12}E) + \dots c_n (H_{1n} - S_{1n}E) &= 0 \\ \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot \\ c_1 (H_{n1} - S_{n1}E) + c_2 (H_{n2} - S_{n2}E) + \dots c_n (H_{nn} - S_{nn}E) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (3.4)$$

Where we have the Coulomb integral

$$H_{ii} = \int \Psi_i H \Psi_i d\tau = \alpha_i$$

which represents the energy of an electron in a 2p orbital on atom i . Also, the resonance or bond integral

$$H_{ij} = \int \Psi_i H \Psi_j d\tau = \beta_{ij}$$

that represents the interaction energy of two atomic orbitals on atoms i and j . With α_i and β_{ij} being negative energy quantities. Finally the overlap integral

$$S_{ij} = \int \Psi_i \Psi_j d\tau$$

in the simplest approximation, is taken to be 1 if $i = j$, and 0 otherwise. For a π system involving only carbon atoms, $\alpha_i = \alpha$, then the secular equations take the form:

$$\begin{array}{cccc} c_1(\alpha - E) + & c_2\beta_{12} + & \dots & c_n\beta_{1n} = 0 \\ \cdot & & & \cdot \\ \cdot & & & \cdot \\ \cdot & & & \cdot \\ c_1\beta_{n1} + & c_2\beta_{n2} + & \dots & c_n(\alpha - E) = 0 \end{array} \quad (3.5)$$

The trivial solution of this equations is $c_1 = c_2 = c_n = 0$. However we are interested in the non-trivial solution which emerges only if the corresponding secular determinant vanishes:

$$\begin{vmatrix} \alpha - E & \beta_{12} & \dots & \beta_{1n} \\ \cdot & & & \cdot \\ \cdot & & & \cdot \\ \cdot & & & \cdot \\ \beta_{n1} & \beta_{n2} & \dots & \alpha - E \end{vmatrix} = 0 \quad (3.6)$$

The key to solve this equations system is the following assumptions:

- All resonance integrals H_{ij} between non-neighboring atoms are set equal to zero.
- All resonance integrals H_{ij} between neighboring atoms are equal and set to β .

Therefore the matrix is reduced to:

$$\begin{vmatrix} \alpha - E & \beta & 0 & & \dots & 0 \\ \beta & \alpha - E & \beta & 0 & & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \beta & \alpha - E & \beta & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \cdot & & \cdot & & & & \cdot \\ \cdot & & & \cdot & & & \cdot \\ \cdot & & & & \cdot & & \cdot \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & \beta & \alpha - E & \beta & 0 \\ 0 & \dots & & 0 & \beta & \alpha - E & \beta \\ 0 & \dots & & & 0 & \beta & \alpha - E \end{vmatrix} = 0 \quad (3.7)$$

The non-trivial solution to this system of equations is the energy corresponding to the molecular orbitals plus α as a constant. It is important to note the significant disadvantage that in this model, electron-electron repulsion is not calculated.

3.4 Studied molecules

One-dimensional molecular wires are constructed with a conjugated carbons chain (from four to ten carbon atoms) that can terminate in either an sp^3 or sp^2 hybridization state. All wires exhibit trans-isomerism.

We attempted to assess several positions for cation(s) approach, but some encountered convergence issues, particularly when dealing with more than two cations. The cations tested included lithium(+1) and sodium(+1). For molecules with more than two cations, the convergence was achieved only with the help of solvent, then we used the CPCM(WATER) keyword in the input.

To study the spin distribution, we compelled the calculations into the triplet state, yielding diverse results by splitting the orbitals into alpha and beta spin states.

Figure 3.3: Studied wires. Atom colors; grey: carbon and white: hydrogen

Chapter 4

Results and Discussion

4.1 Spin and Charge in cation-less systems

Neutral molecules are characterized by the absence of a net charge. However, electrons within the molecule are not evenly distributed; they exhibit a preference for specific locations guided by the electronegativity of the constituent atoms. Each atom type possesses its own electronegativity value, with higher electronegativity resulting in greater electron density around that atom. In cases where atoms within a molecule share the same nature and, consequently, the same electronegativity, other factors come into play to influence electron distribution. These factors include bonding order, hybridized state, resonance, steric effects, among others.

Since the electron spin is an intrinsic property, a hypothesis appears, that the region with higher electron density also exhibit greater spin density. The two possible states of spin are equally probable as long as there are not other influence (e.g. external magnetic field or zero field splitting) therefore in the first instance no polarization is expected. To inspect this, the spin and charge distribution in molecular wires were studied. The Mulliken Population Analysis from DFT calculations allows for the quantification of charge and spin density over each atom. This algorithm partitions the total density of the molecule by assigning basis functions to specific atoms based on the overlap of basis functions[62].

In the table 4.1, the spin and negative charge population is depicted. The table has the two most negative and the two most positive values for charge and spin population, for the fourth, seventh and tenth carbon, in cases where ends in sp^2 and sp^3 hybridization, and also the results for singlet and triplet states. We first observe that the electron density is weakly polarized toward the terminal carbons of the chain, irrespective of the number of carbons or the hybridization state. Later, as the spin is associated with electrons, we anticipate that over the same electronically polarized carbons, spin concentration will occur. Upon analyzing table 4.1, we note that when the chain terminates with an sp^2 carbon, both charge and spin are concentrated on the terminals carbons. Unexpectedly, when the chain ends with an sp^3 carbon, the charge remains concentrated on that carbon, but the spin is concentrated toward the nearest sp^2 carbon atom.

The electron polarization exhibits similar values between both terminal carbons, indicating that there is no preferential carbon ending in the same chain. Additionally, these values remain consistent across carbon chains of different sizes, suggesting that the chain size does not influence the intensity of electron polarization.

The spin population is analysed over the alpha (up) state, as we have triplet multiplicity there are two unpaired up spins, the concentration of these spin states is represented with the positives values in the spin population. So, the value of spin density gets smaller according as the chain length, see fig 4.1. The ten carbons chains has up to less than 41% spin polarization in comparison to the smallest chain. Is important note that when the chain ends in sp^3 carbon, the spin population is located in the closest sp^2 carbon, as can be see in fig 4.2 .

Total # C	Hybridization	Multiplicity	Charge		Spin	
4	sp^2	1	-0.230	-0.230		
		3	-0.242	-0.242	0.941	0.941
	sp^3	1	-0.218	-0.218		
		3	-0.235	-0.235	0.931	0.931
7	sp^2-sp^3	1	-0.239	-0.261		
		3	-0.244	-0.259	0.754	0.741
10	sp^2	1	-0.235	-0.235		
		3	-0.239	-0.239	0.553	0.553
	sp^3	1	-0.230	-0.230		
		3	-0.231	-0.231	0.590	0.590

Table 4.1: Mulliken Population Analysis, for chains with four, seven, and ten carbon atoms. The table has the two most negative and the two most positive values for charge and spin population correspondingly. For chains with odd number of carbon one end is sp^2 and the other is sp^3 .

Figure 4.1: Visual representation of spin up population, note that the spin population in ending carbons decreases as the chain length increases. Blue zones has higher value in spin up population

Figure 4.2: Left: negative charge population (red zones more concentrated) and right: spin population (blue zones more concentrated). The spin population tend to concentrated over the sp^2 terminal carbons. On the other hand, the negative charge population is distributed on the double bonds

For open shell molecules we have the possibility to analyze the alpha and beta orbitals. The Fig. 4.3 shows the alpha and beta orbitals for seven carbon chain. Qualitatively the orbitals looks very similar. But if we compare the number of alpha and beta electrons a light spin polarization was found. The total number of electron in the system is 52 electrons, with 27α and 25β . This polarization is result for the input indications, since we ordered that the system had a triplet multiplicity.

Figure 4.3: HOMO-LUMO and alpha-beta orbitals of buta-1,3-diene with a triplet multiplicity. Atom colors; grey: carbon and white: hydrogen

4.1.1 Energy calculus with Hückel

Buta-1,3-diene

$$H = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha & \beta & 0 & 0 \\ \beta & \alpha & \beta & 0 \\ 0 & \beta & \alpha & \beta \\ 0 & 0 & \beta & \alpha \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.1)$$

Secular equations

$$H = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha - E & \beta & 0 & 0 \\ \beta & \alpha - E & \beta & 0 \\ 0 & \beta & \alpha - E & \beta \\ 0 & 0 & \beta & \alpha - E \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} C_1 \\ C_2 \\ C_3 \\ C_4 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.2)$$

$$H = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\alpha - E}{\beta} & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & \frac{\alpha - E}{\beta} & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & \frac{\alpha - E}{\beta} & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & \frac{\alpha - E}{\beta} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} C_1 \\ C_2 \\ C_3 \\ C_4 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.3)$$

Taking $x = \frac{\alpha - E}{\beta}$

$$H = \begin{bmatrix} x & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & x & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & x & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & x \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} C_1 \\ C_2 \\ C_3 \\ C_4 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.4)$$

Solutions when $\det |H| = 0$

$$x \begin{bmatrix} x & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & x & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & x \end{bmatrix} - 1 \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & x & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & x \end{bmatrix} + 0 \begin{bmatrix} 1 & x & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & x \end{bmatrix} + 0 \begin{bmatrix} 1 & x & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & x \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} = 0 \quad (4.5)$$

$$x * x \begin{bmatrix} x & 1 \\ 1 & x \end{bmatrix} - x * 1 \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & x \end{bmatrix} + x * 0 \begin{bmatrix} 1 & x \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} = x^2(x^2 - 1) - x^2 \quad (4.6)$$

$$1 * 1 \begin{bmatrix} x & 1 \\ 1 & x \end{bmatrix} - 1 * 1 \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 0 & x \end{bmatrix} + 0 * 1 \begin{bmatrix} 0 & x \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} = x^2 - 1 \quad (4.7)$$

$$\det |H| = x^2(x^2 - 1) - x^2 - (x^2 - 1) = x^4 - 3x^2 + 1 = 0$$

$$\text{if } X = x^2, \text{ then } X^2 - 3X + 1 = 0$$

Solved, $X \approx 2.618$ and 0.382

Replace $x = \pm\sqrt{X}$, obtain $x = \pm 0.618$ and $x = \pm 1.618$

So, expected energies be:

$$E_1 = \alpha + 1.618\beta$$

$$E_2 = \alpha + 0.618\beta$$

$$E_3 = \alpha - 0.618\beta$$

$$E_4 = \alpha - 1.618\beta$$

The HOMO-LUMO gap can be obtained subtracting the $E_3 - E_2$. Then is 1.236β .

Deca-1,3,5,7,9-pentaene

$$H = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha & \beta & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \beta & \alpha & \beta & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \beta & \alpha & \beta & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \beta & \alpha & \beta & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \beta & \alpha & \beta & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \beta & \alpha & \beta & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \beta & \alpha & \beta & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \beta & \alpha & \beta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \beta & \alpha & \beta \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \beta & \alpha \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.8)$$

Secular equations

$$H = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\alpha-E}{\beta} & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & \frac{\alpha-E}{\beta} & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & \frac{\alpha-E}{\beta} & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & \frac{\alpha-E}{\beta} & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & \frac{\alpha-E}{\beta} & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & \frac{\alpha-E}{\beta} & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & \frac{\alpha-E}{\beta} & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & \frac{\alpha-E}{\beta} & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & \frac{\alpha-E}{\beta} & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & \frac{\alpha-E}{\beta} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} C_1 \\ C_2 \\ C_3 \\ C_4 \\ C_5 \\ C_6 \\ C_7 \\ C_8 \\ C_9 \\ C_{10} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.9)$$

Taking $x = \frac{\alpha-E}{\beta}$

$$H = \begin{bmatrix} x & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & x & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & x & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & x & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & x & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & x & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & x & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & x & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & x & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & x \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} C_1 \\ C_2 \\ C_3 \\ C_4 \\ C_5 \\ C_6 \\ C_7 \\ C_8 \\ C_9 \\ C_{10} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.10)$$

Solutions when $\det |H| = 0$

Obtain $x = \pm 1.683$, $x = \pm 0.285$, $x = \pm 1.310$, $x = \pm 1.919$, and $x = \pm 0.831$

So, expected energies be:

$$\begin{aligned} E_1 &= \alpha + 1.919\beta \\ E_2 &= \alpha + 1.683\beta \\ E_3 &= \alpha + 1.310\beta \\ E_4 &= \alpha + 0.831\beta \\ E_5 &= \alpha + 0.285\beta \\ E_6 &= \alpha - 0.285\beta \\ E_7 &= \alpha - 0.831\beta \\ E_8 &= \alpha - 1.310\beta \\ E_9 &= \alpha - 1.683\beta \\ E_{10} &= \alpha - 1.919\beta \end{aligned}$$

The HOMO-LUMO gap can be obtained subtracting the $E_6 - E_5$. Then is 0.570β . Comparing with the HOMO-LUMO gap obtaining in four carbon wires this gap is reduced in 54.8%. We can notice that these results are in agreement with the literature[1], thus as length and conjugation increase the gap is reduced. In large molecules there are

a greater number of molecular orbitals, and the more amount of orbitals the energy levels become more closely spaced, therefore, the HOMO-LUMO gap is reduced. A smaller HOMO-LUMO gap is associated with improved electrical conductivity in molecular wires. It allows for easier movement of electrons, contributing to enhanced electronic transport properties.

Here, we investigate how the reduction of the HOMO-LUMO gap varies with chain length, acknowledging its sensitivity to multiple factors. Additionally, the presence of neighboring molecules can significantly influence the energetic levels of the orbitals. When a cation is in proximity, its orbitals interact with those of the chain, leading to orbital mixing. Initially, one might expect a charge transfer between the cation and the chain, where the positive charge of the cation attracts the delocalized electrons from the chain. Consequently, like the electron positions determine the orbital shapes, the value of the HOMO-LUMO gap is altered. This orbital mixing can indeed reduce the HOMO-LUMO gap, but it may also weaken the π -conjugated system due to the charge transfer phenomenon.

4.1.2 CASPT2 results

The CASPT2 provides various roots, encompassing all possible configurations within the CAS. Despite the expectation that configurations with higher weight represent the molecule's basal state, filled the orbital energy, and the Pauli exclusion principle, our findings indicate that configurations with single occupied orbitals bear more weight.

For instance, the CAS(4,4) calculation for buta-1,3-diene, with symmetry A_g and the first four roots calculated in a 4x4 matrix, yields four tables, each displaying the heaviest configuration for a particular root. Table 4.2 presents the results for the first root. The first column enumerates the configurations, the second and third columns denote the CAS orbital occupation in their respective symmetry and alpha/beta state, and the last column represents the weight assigned to each configuration in root 1. Notably, the heaviest configuration is number six, characterized by all four orbitals being single-occupied. Despite prior expectations based on conventional wisdom, where filling the lowest energy orbitals doubly is assumed to be more stable, the CAS result challenges this notion. The CAS orbitals, being the π -conjugated orbitals, possess similar energies. In this scenario, combining two opposite-spin electrons in the same orbital is found to be less stable than distributing the four electrons among the four orbitals, highlighting the nuanced behavior of the system.

conf/sym	22	33	Weight
1	22	00	0.06364
2	20	20	0.03409
3	20	ud	0.13150
4	20	02	0.02315
5	ud	20	0.14880
6	ud	ud	0.23080
7	ud	02	0.04141
8	02	20	0.03457
9	02	ud	0.04589
10	02	02	0.00334
11	uu	dd	0.15730
12	00	22	0.08552

Table 4.2: CI-coefficients larger than 0.05 for root 1 with their respective weight. The second and third column indicate the alpha/beta state in each symmetry. Fourth column is the weight corresponding to each configuration present in the root 1

Is possible calculate the CAS 4,4 without symmetry. The table 4.3 shows the results for buta-1,3-diene without symmetry. The occupation in each configuration varies significantly when compared with the case of calculus with symmetry. In this case, the heaviest configuration is the number two, with one orbital double occupied and two single occupied. This configuration is closer to the ones expected following the Pauli's principle. As we can notice the roots are highly dependent on the input parameters. The results can be have accurate but is important understand the studied system and what we want to know.

conf	1111	Weight
2	2ud0	0.49482
3	2u0d	0.00914
9	ud20	0.00925
10	udud	0.12403
11	ud02	0.00729
15	uudd	0.03681
18	ou2d	0.00715
19	oud2	0.31151

Table 4.3: CI-coefficients larger than 0.05 for root 1 with their respective weight. The second column indicate the alpha/beta state. Third column is the weight corresponding to each configuration present in the root 1

The outcome is highly contingent on how root conditions are specified. Therefore, a comprehensive exploration of various configurations is essential to identify those closely resembling a basal state that aligns with the electron filling dictated by the Pauli exclusion principle.

In systems where orbitals exhibit similar energies, the superposition of states are more pronounced. In such cases, configurations with single occupied orbitals can significantly contribute to the system. Consequently, a profound understanding of the system and its orbitals is paramount to effectively discriminate between different configurations obtained in CASPT2 calculations.

4.2 One cation effect on molecular wires

The cation has several possibilities for approaching the chains, and evidently, the features of the chains depend on its positioning. Therefore, we selected two possible cation locations. In the fig. 4.4, the position one is next to the end of the chain, and position two is in the middle of the chain. These positions were tested for all chain lengths.

Figure 4.4: Possible cation position in the molecule plane. Atoms colors; grey: carbon, white: hydrogen and lilac: lithium

Through the optimization process using the DFT method, the system searches for the most stable location of the cation, which may not always align with the proposed positions one and two. Generally, when the cation is placed in position one and is next to an sp^3 carbon, the position is maintained after optimization. In contrast, when the cation is adjacent to an sp^2 carbon, it relocates above the first double bond, see Fig.4.5. The higher electron density from the double bonds attracts the cation. In cases where the chain terminates in an sp^3 carbon, the cation does not feel the same level of attraction, resulting in an unchanged optimized structure.

Figure 4.5: Cation position after optimization; in ten carbons chains. Atoms colors; grey: carbon, white: hydrogen and lilac: lithium

The impact of the cation can be quantified through the analysis of charges and spin distribution along the chain, the data are summarized in table 4.4. When compared the systems without cations, where the extreme carbons exhibit very similar values, the presence of a nearby cation results in the concentration of negative charge over the carbon nearest to the cation, see fig. 4.6. In chains ending with a sp^3 carbon, the charge polarization is more pronounced than in those ending with sp^2 , compare the two electrostatic potential maps in fig. 4.6, whereas the difference in spin population is higher in chains ending with sp^2 , that is the sp^2 endings carbon are more easily polarizable. Additionally, the multiplicity does not seem to significantly influence the charge population. The spin tendency remains consistent (decreasing as the chain lengthens), albeit with lower values, but a special observation is done over the chains ending with a sp^3 carbon, here the carbons have close values of spin population in spite of the presence of cation. This is due to the spin population in sp^3 ending chain, which is moved to the closest sp^2 carbon, see fig. 4.2, and that carbon is further away from the cation and therefore does not feel its influence in the same way as chains that end in sp^2 carbons, where we can see that one of the carbons has up to 12% more spin population than the one at the other end.

Total # C	Hybridization	Multiplicity	Charge		Spin	
4	sp^2	1	-0.172	-0.188		
		3	-0.196	-0.190	0.911	0.809
	sp^3	1	-0.214	-0.424		
		3	-0.219	-0.428	0.913	0.910
7	sp^2 - sp^3	1	-0.339	-0.434		
		3	-0.451	-0.349	0.736	0.629
10	sp^2	1	-0.443	-0.499		
		3	-0.451	-0.361	0.470	0.565
	sp^3	1	-0.225	-0.413		
		3	-0.224	-0.381	0.541	0.535

Table 4.4: Mulliken Population Analysis, for chains with one cation (Li^+) in position one; with four, seven, and ten carbon atoms. The table has the two most negative and the two most positive values for charge and spin population correspondingly

Figure 4.6: Electrostatic potential maps for four carbon atoms chain, in cases where ending in sp^2 (right) and sp^3 (left) hybridization, with a cation in position one. The ending sp^3 carbon become more polarized, its is evident if we compare the ending carbons close to the cation; strong green color over the sp^3 carbon versus lighter green color over sp^2 carbon

The results for charge and spin in systems with a cation in position two are described in Table 4.5. In this configuration, the middle carbons exhibit the highest negative charge concentration, thanks to the positive charge above them. The carbon closest to the cation possesses the highest negative charge. Conversely, the two spin population values are quite similar in the same chain, for cases where chain has even number carbon atoms, resulting in two carbons being equally polarized. The chains with odd number of carbon atoms does not have the similar population, it differs in 12%, due the asymmetric distribution of π orbitals. The trend observed here is as the chain length increases the middle carbons are more negative, however their spin population decreases until 40% when pass for four carbon chain to ten carbon chain.

Total # C	Hybridization	Multiplicity	Charge		Spin	
4	sp^2	1	-0.233	-0.194		
		3	-0.207	-0.222	0.911	0.930
	sp^3	1	-0.320	-0.261		
		3	-0.232	-0.238	0.876	0.875
7	sp^2 - sp^3	1	-0.358	-0.319		
		3	-0.275	-0.395	0.756	0.640
10	sp^2	1	-0.408	-0.208		
		3	-0.206	-0.370	0.549	0.540
	sp^3	1	-0.350	-0.351		
		3	-0.310	-0.315	0.557	0.556

Table 4.5: Mulliken Population Analysis for chains with one cation (Li^+) in position two; with four, seven, and ten carbon atoms. The table has the two most negative and the two most positive values for charge and spin population correspondingly

To recapitulate, the strategic design of cation placement is crucial to concentrate spin and charge on desired atoms. Cations in position one induce a shift in electron density, maintaining the two most negative charge values on both terminal carbons, with the one closer to the cation exhibiting an even higher negative charge. Conversely, cations in position two alter the charge distribution on the most negative carbons. In this case, the farthest carbon acquires a positive charge, while the negative charge becomes predominantly concentrated on the middle carbons. This distinction arises because the cation in position two, being close to both double bonds, readily interacts with their electron density. In contrast, the cation in position one, proximity to only one double bond, primarily influences that specific bond, resulting in the observed changes.

4.2.1 Alpha and beta orbitals in molecules with perpendicular cation position

The alpha and beta orbitals for chains in the triplet state are illustrated in Fig. 4.7. The orbitals closest to the cation exhibit deformation, with their new shape pointing towards the cation. This response is expected due to the electrostatic interaction between the cation and the electrons. Orbitals are not fixed structures; they represent spatial regions that adapt to the electronic population. Therefore, if electrons experience any perturbation, such as attraction or repulsion, causing a change in their original paths, the shape of the orbitals will also be altered.

One difference in alpha and beta orbitals is the spin population, the molecule with a triplet state has two unpaired electrons in two alpha orbitals, whereas the beta orbitals remain “empty”. This unpaired electrons feels the positive charge of cation and therefore will attract, so deforming the alpha orbitals much more than beta orbitals. This alpha and beta orbital deformation for HOMO and LUMO are depicted in fig. 4.7.

In the alpha-HOMO orbital, electron delocalization is more pronounced compared to the beta-HOMO orbital. Particularly, in the left side (associated with the sp^3 carbon ending), a significant portion of the orbitals is present in the alpha-HOMO orbital, which is not observed to the same extent in the beta-HOMO orbital. As a result, the spins in the alpha state tend to be more localized towards the left side. Therefore, it is important to note that the localization of electrons in the alpha-spin state differs from that of the beta-spin state.

The shape of the orbitals is of utmost importance because it determines the HOMO-LUMO gap, and consequently, a myriad of chemical processes. For example, as mentioned earlier, conductivity is facilitated with a smaller gap size. Processes like absorption and emission of light are also influenced by the size of this gap[63]. The REDOX potentials can be tailored by adjusting the size of that gap [64].

Figure 4.7: Cation position after optimization; in ten carbons chains. Atoms colors; grey: carbon, white: hydrogen and lilac: lithium

4.2.2 HOMO-LUMO gap

As it mention before, the HOMO-LUMO gap is very important to a wide variety of phenomenon. The table 4.6 and 4.7, shows the energies values for HOMO and LUMO, and the gap. These values are taken for Hepta-1,3,5-triene molecule in single and triplet state, alone and with cation. First, in the case with lithium the energy of HOMO and LUMO is reduced in comparison to the case without the cation, also the energy gap is reduced by 0.19 eV. The orbitals of cation and molecule mix changing their energy values, thus the lithium orbitals stabilize the energies of the orbitals of the wire alone. A reduction of the gap is desired for improve the conductivity in wires.

When the molecule is in triplet state there is a differentiation in alpha and beta orbitals. However the change in energy value for alpha and alpha (with cation) and beta and beta (with cation) are very similar, around 4eV in the four cases. Contrary to the singlet case, here the HOMO-LUMO gap increases in presence of cation. The reason may be that we have empty and single occupied orbitals, the single occupied orbitals interact more with the cation causing a greater difference between HOMO and LUMO, hence when we add the cation the gap increases 0.17 eV. In the case of empty or beta orbitals, the gap also increases, but not as much as when they are single occupied, only a 0.11 eV.

	Hepta-1,3,5-triene	Hepta-1,3,5-triene + Li^+
LUMO	-1.357	-5.997
HOMO	-5.696	-10.143
Gap	4.339	4.145

Table 4.6: Enery (eV) for HOMO-LUMO orbitals in Hepta-1,3,5-triene in singlet multiplicity

	Hepta-1,3,5-triene		Hepta-1,3,5-triene + Li^+	
	Alpha	Beta	Alpha	Beta
LUMO	-3.839	-0.924	-8.057	-5.470
HOMO	-6.210	-3.293	-10.601	-7.945
Gap	2.371	2.369	2.544	2.475

Table 4.7: Enery (eV) for HOMO-LUMO and alpha-beta orbitals in Hepta-1,3,5-triene in triplet multiplicity

4.3 Comparing two cation nature: Li^+ and Na^+

The sodium was optimized in the same position as the lithium, so all the changes observed must be due to the different in charge and the level of the orbitals between lithium and sodium. The data are summarized in the table 4.8.

The trends observed with lithium are mirrored in the presence of sodium, albeit with lower values of charge and spin population. This suggests that both alkali metals influence the electronic environment of carbon, though the effect of sodium is less pronounced. When sodium interacts with the carbon structure, the negative charge and spin density are distributed more evenly across the carbons, unlike the concentrated localization seen with lithium.

This disparity in behavior can be attributed to the difference in ionic potential between lithium and sodium. Although both carry a +1 charge, lithium's smaller size results in a higher charge density and a more exposed nucleus. This intensified electrostatic attraction allows lithium to more effectively draw electron density towards itself, leading to a more concentrated accumulation of charge and spin near the lithium cation. In contrast, sodium's larger size and lower charge density result in a weaker interaction, causing the charge and spin to be dispersed more evenly across the carbon structure[65].

If the objective is to customize the electronic structure of a molecule, the choice of the cation becomes crucial in achieving the desired alterations. When lithium is in proximity, the terminal carbon exhibits a more negative charge compared to when sodium is present. Conversely, the variation in alpha-spin population is more pronounced when sodium is nearby, resulting in lower alpha-spin population on the terminal carbons compared to when lithium is present or when the chain is in isolation. In essence, while both lithium and sodium interact with carbon, the degree and nature of this interaction are modulated by the subtle differences in their ionic potentials. Lithium's smaller size and higher charge density lead to a more localized and intense effect, whereas sodium's larger size and lower charge density result in a more diffuse and less pronounced impact.

Total # C	Hybridization	Multiplicity	Charge		Spin	
4	sp^2	1	-0.185	-0.158		
		3	-0.208	-0.180	0.921	0.871
	sp^3	1	-0.215	-0.390		
		3	-0.222	-0.396	0.909	0.930
7	sp^2-sp^3	1	-0.268	-0.328		
		3	-0.359	-0.337	0.732	0.658
10	sp^2	1	-0.339	-0.292		
		3	-0.356	-0.290	0.515	0.553
	sp^3	1	-0.226	-0.389		
		3	-0.220	-0.234	0.436	0.443

Table 4.8: Mulliken Population Analysis, for chains with one cation (Na^+) in position one; with four, seven, and ten carbon atoms. The table has the two most negative and the two most positive values for charge and spin population correspondingly

4.4 More than one cation, simple addition or synergy?

The optimization of the structures with more than two cations were complicated. The convergence problems could be overcome by adding a solvent model. The fig. 4.8 depicted some of the wires tested with two and four cations.

Figure 4.8: Wires with two and four cations (Li^+). Atoms colors; grey: carbon, white: hydrogen and lilac: lithium

The values of negative charge and spin population are concentrated at the ends of

the chain, as shown in table 4.1. There is no preferential carbon when cations approach from both ends of the chains, and both carbons exhibit similar values of charge and spin population.

However, as the chain length increases, the negative charge population also increases. The π -conjugated system in ten-carbon chains is larger and, therefore, more polarizable in the presence of cations. On the other hand, the spin population follows the opposite trend; as the length increases, the spin population decreases.

Total # C	Hybridization	Multiplicity	Charge		Spin	
4	sp^2	1	-0.158	-0.159		
		3	-0.140	-0.140	0.923	0.923
	sp^3	1	-0.404	-0.403		
		3	-0.383	-0.337	0.925	0.923
7	sp^2 - sp^3	1	-0.716	-0.327		
		3	-0.703	-0.458	0.669	0.722
10	sp^2	1	-0.343	-0.343		
		3	-0.535	-0.535	0.515	0.515
	sp^3	1	-0.411	-0.412		
		3	-0.405	-0.405	0.575	0.574

Table 4.9: Mulliken Population Analysis, for chains with two cations (Li^+); with four, seven, and ten carbon atoms. The table has the two most negative and the two most positive values for charge and spin population correspondingly

In chains with four carbons and four cations, all the negative charge is concentrated at the terminal carbons, while the middle carbons carry a positive charge, see fig. 4.9. The influence of four cations is sufficient to polarize the entire molecule. However, as the chain length increases, more than four cations are required to achieve the same result. In chains with ten carbons, the terminal carbons are negatively polarized, but some of the other carbons also carry a negative charge. The spin population follow the same trend as the previous cases, but with a particular quality, both spin polarized carbons have exactly the same population value, positive charges direct population consistently to the two carbons.

Total # C	Hybridization	Multiplicity	Charge		Spin	
4	sp^2	1	-0.777	-0.780		
		3	-0.708	-0.707	0.887	0.887
	sp^3	1	-0.461	-0.361		
10	sp^2	1	-0.433	-0.436		
		3	-0.669	-0.700	0.509	0.506
	sp^3	1	-0.344	-0.344		
		3	-0.342	-0.342	0.593	0.593

Table 4.10: Mulliken Population Analysis, for chains with four cations (Li^+); with four, seven, and ten carbon atoms. The table has the two most negative and the two most positive values for charge and spin population correspondingly

Figure 4.9: Electrostatic potential surface for four and ten carbons chain with four cations. The negative charge population is dispersed more evenly in longer chains

In short chains, a greater charge polarization will be observed with four cations, while in longer chains, two cations can polarize the chain more effectively. It is important to note that the hybridization state of the carbon influences its polarizability; sp^2 carbons are more polarizable than sp^3 carbons.

The spin concentration follows the previously analyzed trend. The longer the chain, the lower the population of alpha-spin over ending carbons. Additionally, long chains are more easily polarized when more cations are added, especially in sp^3 -terminated chains. Therefore, concentrating the spin population over a specific carbon in long chains requires more than one cation.

The distortion produced by the presence of multiple cations can be quantified by the changes in the HOMO-LUMO gap, as analyzed in Table 4.11. The addition of multiple cations causes significant distortions in the molecular orbitals. The electrons in the π -system lose some of their conjugation and become more localized, leading to increased localization of the orbitals themselves. Consequently, the overlap between orbitals weakens, and the HOMO-LUMO gap increases compared to the case of one or no cations (see table 4.7, where the π -system not very affected).

	Trans-butadiene + $2Li^+$		Trans-butadiene + $4Li^+$	
	Alpha	Beta	Alpha	Beta
LUMO	-8.328	-10.918	-2.198	-5.613
HOMO	-11.383	-15.114	-5.735	-9.560
Gap	3.055	4.196	3.537	3.947

Table 4.11: Energy (eV) for HOMO-LUMO and alpha-beta orbitals in Trans-butadiene with two and four cations and in triplet multiplicity

4.4.1 Geometry changes

The cations have an obvious influence on the electronic structure of the molecules and on the orbitals, and these changes can be accompanied by structural changes. A graphical analysis can be conducted in Fig. 4.10 to examine the geometry after the addition of cations.

Depending the size of molecule one or two cations could be enough to blend the planar structure. The structural change is joined with a changes in the bonds that can be enlarge or small the HOMO-LUMO gap.

Figure 4.10: Geometry changes for the presence of cations

Both the electronic properties and the geometry can be modified thanks to the addition of cations.

4.5 Proposing a strategy for design with cations affecting spins: key parameters

Having qualitatively and quantitatively analyzed charge and spin population changes induced by cations, we can develop strategies to achieve desired charge and spin modifications.

The first and crucial step is understanding the intrinsic properties of the system, including its orbital and electronic structure. These properties determine the ground-state spin configuration and the possible pathways for spin manipulation. A thorough understanding of the electronic band structure, including the filling of energy levels and the presence of magnetic interactions, is essential. Additionally, factors like symmetry and the presence of local environments can significantly influence spin states. By carefully examining these inherent characteristics, we can establish a foundation for selecting appropriate cations and tailoring their introduction strategy to achieve the desired spin modification.

The molecules studied here are one-dimensional wires composed of conjugated carbon chains. Several important parameters influence these systems:

1. Number of Carbons: This can result in an even or odd number of carbons. Chains with an odd number of carbons have lower symmetry, and their orbitals are not equally distributed on the left and right sides
2. Hybridization State of Carbons: The sp^2 -hybridized terminal carbons will have a higher electron density compared to sp^3 -hybridized terminal carbons.
3. Chain Length: Longer chains have a greater degree of electron delocalization. These delocalized electrons are more susceptible to external perturbations.

Second, we need to define the expected change. We have already demonstrated that the presence of cations alters spin, charge population, orbital shapes (alpha and beta), and the HOMO-LUMO gap. Additionally, in specific cases, cations can even induce geometric changes. Therefore, before beginning our work, we must clearly define the specific modifications we anticipate.

Thus, once we thoroughly understand the system and have clearly defined our desired modifications, we can initiate calculations. Our previous analysis provides a framework for targeted modifications, but it is essential to do simulations to verify factors like optimal cation positioning, distance, quantity, and specific type of cation. Here is why this refinement is crucial:

- Site-Specific Effects: The atom closest to the cation, particularly if it is an sp^2 carbon, will experience the most significant alterations in its properties. The degree of modification decreases with distance from the cation. We can strategically employ this distance dependence: placing the cation near one end of the chain will induce

a gradient in spin and charge population, creating distinct properties at each end of the chain, or on the contrary, positioning the cation at the center of the chain will result in more symmetrical modifications on both sides.

- **Concentration Dependence:** Increasing the concentration of cations will generally increase the magnitude of electronic modification. However, excessive cation concentrations may disrupt the molecule's geometry. Larger molecules might accommodate multiple cations to achieve effects similar to those observed in smaller molecules with a single cation.
- **Cation Specificity:** Cations with different sizes, charges, and electronic configurations can induce distinct effects on electronic states. In this case, Li^{+1} cations likely produce greater charge changes due to their smaller size and higher charge density, allowing for stronger interactions. On the other hand, the cation Na^{+1} alters more the spin population specially in longer chains.

In most cases, the spin population is concentrated on the terminal carbons. This concentration decreases naturally with increasing chain length, and the addition of cations further contributes to this decrease. Therefore, cations could be strategically used to delocalize these unpaired electrons throughout the chain.

The presence of cations also influences charge distribution. Atoms in proximity to the cation exhibit a higher concentration of negative charge. This effect is more pronounced in longer chains due to their increased number of delocalized electrons. This charge redistribution can potentially impact the system's reactivity and interactions with other molecules or fields.

Another result shows that the addition of cations modifies the HOMO-LUMO gap. To minimize the HOMO-LUMO gap, cations should be positioned near the regions of HOMO and LUMO concentration. Note that close proximity may induce geometric changes in the molecule, potentially altering its planar structure.

In summary, successful modification of conjugated molecular wires depends on meticulous analysis of the target system's inherent properties (hybridization, orbitals, energy levels) prior to the introduction of cations. This foundational understanding is essential for interpreting and quantifying induced changes, along with choosing appropriate cations and strategies (placement, distance, concentration) to achieve the desired modifications in electronic and spin properties. Our investigation highlights the complex interplay between chain length, sp^2/sp^3 termination, carbon count, and spin multiplicity states, emphasizing the need for a tailored analytical approach.

Chapter 5

Conclusions

The studied molecular wires exhibit clear relationships between chain length, hybridization, symmetry, and both spin and charge population. As chain length increases, the HOMO-LUMO gap decreases, enhancing conductivity. Longer chains also possess larger conjugated π -systems promoting stronger interactions with cations. Terminal carbons consistently exhibit the highest negative charge. However, spin-up population concentrates on terminal carbons only with sp^2 hybridization. In sp^3 -terminated chains, spin population centers on the nearest sp^2 carbons and decreases with increasing chain length. Chain symmetry is also crucial: odd-numbered chains possess an unpaired electron on the central carbon, creating asymmetry compared to even-numbered chains.

Spin population exhibits a clear chain-length dependence, with longer chains generally displaying reduced spin-up populations compared to shorter ones, the ten carbon chains has until 37% less spin-up concentration in their ending carbons. Introducing a cation near the wire significantly alters spin distribution, concentrating it on the carbon nearest to the cation. This cation-induced spin localization is particularly pronounced in sp^2 -terminated chains. In triplet-state molecules, cation presence primarily distorts alpha orbitals due to their occupancy, which consequentially impacts the HOMO-LUMO gap.

Although lithium and sodium cations induce qualitatively similar spin distribution changes, their size disparity plays a crucial role. Lithium's smaller size allows for stronger interactions with nearby electrons, potentially leading to more pronounced spin manipulation effects compared to sodium. Therefore, for scenarios requiring significant manipulation of spin-up populations, lithium cations might be the preferred choice.

Cation placement and quantity significantly influence molecular wire structure. Cations positioned too close to the chain induce deformations such as bending. This effect intensifies with multiple cations. The concentration of negative charge in the short chains is more than 2 times greater than in the long chains using the same number of cations, therefore to achieve the same effect on the long chains even more cations would be needed, risking this leading to structural deformations. Concerning to the spin-up population this only changes when the chain is short, in long chains we have a spin population practically the same as when there is no cation.

These conclusions demonstrate that spin and charge distribution within molecular wires can be strategically manipulated through the introduction of cations. Understanding the molecule's intrinsic properties, along with careful analysis of cation-induced changes, enables the design of tailored molecular systems with precisely tuned spin characteristics.

The implementation of spin sensors on next generation technologies can improve significantly the informatics in capacity of calculus and operations. Explore these achievements experimentally can contribute to these new technologies age. The next step for this work is experimentally prove these findings. Also explore the influence of cations in spin states of more complex molecules. The implementation of spin sensors on next generation technologies can improve significantly the informatics in capacity of calculus and operations. Explore these achievements experimentally can contribute to this new technologies age. The next step for this work is experimentally prove these findings. Also explore the influence of cations in spin states of more complex molecules.

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